

Performance of College Students in Writing and Literature Courses

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Abstract

Previous studies revealed that English language proficiency were affected by certain factors such as sex, courses taken and attendance to remedial courses. This descriptive research dealt with the performance in writing and literature courses of college students at the University of Antique, Tario-Lim Memorial Campus, Academic Year 2011-2012. The subjects were 223 randomly selected students who have grades in English 2 and in English 4. The sources of data included the Report of Enrollment, Metropolitan Achievement Test result sheets, and grade sheets in English 2 and in English 4. Mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent sample, and one-way ANOVA were used as statistics. Alpha level was set at .05 for the two-tailed test. It revealed that college students had “very satisfactory” performance in writing course, except for the males and the Business and Management students who had

“satisfactory” performance. The students also had “very satisfactory” performance in literature course, except for the males who had “satisfactory” performance. Significant differences were noted in the performances in writing and in literature courses of the students grouped according to sex and attendance to remedial course. However, when their courses were considered a significant difference existed in their performance in writing course but none in their performance in literature course. Therefore, sex is a factor that affects students’ performance in these learning areas. Also, course affects students’ performance in writing but not in literature. Further, attendance to a remedial course is not a guarantee that students’ performance in writing and literature would be better than those who are already competent in English.

Keywords: Descriptive research design, writing course, literature course, remedial course, Antique, Philippines

Introduction

In the Philippine education system, English is a subject that develops students’ competencies in the second language. However, performance in this particular subject maybe affected by personal and environmental factors (Hansen, 2000).

Studies on the English language proficiency among college students reveal that language proficiency were affected by certain factors such as sex (Plata, 2009; Hsueh, et al., 2008; Westby, 2006;

Gemora, 2006; Tolentino, 2005), courses taken (Pulmones, 2009; Tolentino, 2005; Villa, 2004), and attendance to remedial courses (Hsiu & Warden, 2009; Nulada, 2006; Tolentino, 2005; Poral, 2004).

It has been noticed that some students at the university level are coming up with very disappointing knowledge in English. Many of these students were found to be poor in English (Garcia, 1999, in Delgado 2008; Han, 1994; and Schmitt and Meara, 1997, in Hunt and Beglar, 2007). As revealed in different studies, these students had problems in pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, and grammar (Hunt and Beglar, 2007; Gemora, 2006; and Padilla, 2005); and they show inefficiency in the knowledge and use of the language, both in receptive (listening and reading) and expressive (speaking and writing) activities.

The existence of remedial or developmental courses is an evidence that many of today's college students are not academically strong enough to manage college-level work and should not have been admitted into college in the first place (Attewel et al., 2006). In fact, students for whom English is a second language are greatly overrepresented in remedial courses (Lavin & Weininger, 1998 in Attewell, et al., 2006).

Remedial or developmental education is widespread. Many colleges and universities offer these courses for students who lack some of the reading, writing, and mathematics skills that are critical for college-level work (Roueche & Roueche, 1999 in Attewel et al., 2006). In fact, studies revealed that remedial courses help in preparing the students succeed in their college-level course work (Attewell, et al., 2006).

At University of Antique, Tario-Lim Memorial Campus (UA TLMC), statistics show that more or less 75 percent of the total number of first year college entrants were not able to pass the Metropolitan Achievement Test and they were made to take English Plus, a non-credit course, in order to provide remedial measures for the English competencies they have not mastered well.

It has been observed that these college freshmen manifest some difficulties specifically in the three skills in the language arts such as speaking, reading and writing. Specifically, some students had a lot of errors in grammar, correct usage and mechanics; and found it difficult to organize their ideas when they are made to write essays. They also found it hard in answering comprehension questions about selections or literary pieces read in class.

Moreover, it was also noted that male and female students in various courses perform differently; and that students from the four colleges – College of Business Education, College of Computer Studies, College of Fisheries, College of Teacher Education and Hospitality Management – at UA TLMC also manifest different learning capabilities.

Hence, this study focused on the performance of college students in writing and literature courses.

Research Objectives

This study looked into the performance of college students in writing and literature courses at University of Antique, Tario-Lim Memorial Campus, academic year 2011-2012.

Specifically, answers to these questions were sought:

1. What is the performance of the college students in writing course when taken as a whole, and when grouped according to sex, curricular program and attendance to remedial course?
2. What is the performance of the college students in literature course when taken as a whole, and when grouped according to sex, curricular program and attendance to remedial course?
3. Is there a significant difference in the performance of college students in writing course when grouped as to sex, curricular program, and attendance to remedial course?
4. Is there a significant difference in the performance of college students in literature course when grouped as to sex, curricular program, and attendance to remedial course?

Theoretical Framework

Language is learned and language maybe affected by personal and environmental factors. This study is anchored on the theory of pragmatism which emphasizes the social aspects of human nature and the extent to which the individual may be formed by thoughtful, deliberative interaction with others, that is sustained by effort (Kneller, 1964 in Delgado 2001).

This also considers the implication of Ausubel's Theory of Meaningful Reception Learning which states that the learner is simply required to comprehend the material and to incorporate it into his cognitive structure so that it is available for either reproduction, related learning, or problem solving at future date. Meaningfulness also depends on personal variables as age, background experiences, socioeconomic status, end educational background (Schunk, 2004).

The present research is also anchored on Lev Vygotsky's Social Development Theory which considers the social environment critical for learning and that integration of social with personal factors produces learning. Its major application involves the concept of instructional scaffolding which refers to the process of controlling task elements that are beyond the learner's capabilities so the learner can focus on and master those features of the task that he or she can grasp quickly (Schunk, 2004). It considers the help or the assistance given by an adult or an expert in order for an individual to reach his or her zone of proximal development, which represents the amount of learning possible by a student given the proper instructional conditions.

Vygotsky's theory suggests that development depends on interaction with people and the tools that the culture provides to help form their own view of the world. There are three ways a cultural tool can be passed from one individual to another. These are through imitative learning, where one person tries to imitate or copy another, through instructed learning which involves remembering the instructions of the teacher and then using the instruction to self-regulate, and through collaborative learning which involves group of peers who strive to understand each other and work together to learn a specific skill (Tomasello, et al., 1993 in Macleod, 1999).

Conceptual Framework

Using the theory of Pragmatism, Ausubel's theory of meaningful reception learning, and Vygotsky's Social Development Theory, the researcher has identified three variables that may influence the performance of college students in writing and literature courses. These factors are sex, course/curricular program, and attendance to remedial course.

Sex or the fact that one is male or female causes much variation on the kind of social environment a child is exposed to. Usually, culturally defined, these differences in behaviour is likewise deemed to affect the performance (Chambers and Schreiders, 2004; Eitle, 2005; Ceballo, McLoyd and Tokogawa, 2004).

Studies on the English language proficiency among college students reveal that language proficiency was also affected by certain factors such as courses taken, and that differences in students' performance exist when students are grouped according to courses pursued (Hsiu & Warden, 2009; Pulmones, 2009; Nulada, 2006; Tolentino, 2005; Villa, 2004).

It is a fact that attendance to remedial course also contributes to the academic success of students, and improved their performance in writing and in literature courses.

Remedial courses, such as English Plus, have proven to be helpful in improving the performance of college students (Tolentino, 2005; Poral, 2004), but that many students who attend remedial courses do improve their skills and complete college despite academic weak spots (Attewell, et al., 2006).

Review of Related Literature

This study dealt with the various literature and researches which supported salient features and served as bases in dealing with the problems of the present study.

A review of articles (Garcia, 2007; Maminta, 2001; Garcia, 1999) and researches revealed the dismal academic performance and the incompetence in English of college students (Hossain, 2012; Pulmones, 2009; Hunt and Beglar, 2007; Al-Bustan & Al-Bustan 2006; Gemora, 2006; Santos, 2005; Lorio

2003 in Tolentino 2004; Baumenn, Kame'enui and Ash, 2003; Mendez, 2003; and Kelly, 1990 in Delgado, 2008). Specifically, many students find difficulties in writing (Rance-Roney, 2011; Bayogos, 2009; Hughes, 2009; Plata, 2009; Apsay 2001 in Punay 2008; Harris, Punay, 2008; Harris, Graham & Mason, 2006; Bautista 2000 in Padilla 2005; Padilla, 2005; Samonte, 2004; Soriano 1986 in Orquinaza, 1990) and in literature (Villa, 2004; Cornel, 2001; Lumbea in Cornel 2001; Zughoul, 1986 in Arellado, 1994).

Some researchers cited the existence of remedial courses or developmental education in different colleges and universities all over the world (Wikipedia, 2011; Attewell, et al., 2006), as well as the rationale or the need for these courses in the tertiary level (Zai & Skerl, 2001). Different views about the offering of remedial courses were also presented (Kozeracki, 2002; Soliday, 2002; Marcus, 2000; Deil-Amen & Rosenbaum, 2002; and Rosenbaum, 2001; Bettinger & Long, 2004; Kozeracki, 2002; Soliday, 2002); as well as evaluating their effectiveness (McCabe, 2000; Attewell, et al., 2006; Wikipedia, 2011).

In the Philippine educational system, the offering of English Plus, as a non-credit course, is supported by some legal bases such as CHED Memorandum Order No. 59, s. 1996 and CHED Memorandum Order No. 52, s. 2007.

The rationale in the offering of this course is supported by the studies on the poor performance of college students as pointed out in various researches (Hunt and Beglar, 2007; Santos, 2005; Poral, 2004; Baumenn, Kame'enui and Ash, 2003; and Kelly, 1990 in Delgado, 2008); and in the articles of Maminta (2001) and Garcia (1999).

It was noted by some researches that remedial courses tend to affect the performance of college students (Attewel, et al. 2006; Tolentino, 2005; Corvera, et al., 2005; Poral, 2004; Adelman, 1999 and 2004; and Zai & Skerl, 2001).

There are also some factors affecting students' performance (Poral, 2004; Shanker, 2003; Savignon, 1983 in Delgado, 2001; Hansen, 2000).

Specifically, studies showed that factors in determining the performance of students in English include sex (Plata, 2009; Hsueh, et al. 2008; Gemora, 2006; Cheesman, Simpson, and Wint, 2006; Nulada, 2006; Westby, 2006; Tolentino, 2005; De Silva, 2002; Rubin, 1980 in Delgado, 2001); course (Arum and Roksa, 2011; Jaschik, 2011; Hsiu and Warden, 2009; Pulmones, 2009; Nulada, 2006; Tolentino, 2005; Villa, 2004;); and attendance to remedial courses (Hsiu & Warden, 2009; Nulada, 2006; Tolentino, 2005; Poral, 2004).

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to look into the performance in writing and in literature courses of college students at the University of Antique, Tario-Lim Memorial Campus, Academic Year 2011-2012.

This employed the descriptive research design.

The independent variables were sex as the personal factor and course/curricular program and attendance to remedial course as the environmental factors; and dependent variables were the performance in writing and performance literature courses.

Subjects of the Study, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The subjects of the study were the 223 randomly selected college students of University of Antique, Tario-Lim Memorial Campus who have grades in English 2 and English 4. They were determined using the proportional random sampling from a population of 505 college students. In determining the sample size, Slovin's formula set at .05 desired margin of error was used.

When categorized as to sex, 67 or 30.00 percent were males, and 156 or 70.00 percent were females.

When classified according to course/curricular program 49 or 22.00 percent were students in Teacher Education, 91 or 40.80 percent in Computer and Information Technology, and 83 or 37.20 percent in Business and Management.

When grouped according to attendance in remedial course, 136 or 61.00 percent attended and 87 or 39.00 percent did not attend English Plus, as a remedial course.

The distribution of the participants is reflected in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of the Participants

Category	n	%
A. Entire Group	223	100.00 %
B. Sex		
Male	67	30.00 %
Female	156	70.00 %
C. Course/Curricular Program		
Teacher Education	49	22.00 %
Computer and Information Technology	91	40.80 %
Business and Management	83	37.20 %
D. Attendance to Remedial Course		
Students who attended English Plus	136	61.00 %
Students who did not attend English Plus	87	39.00 %

Sources of Data

The sources of data in this study included the Record of Enrollment for Academic Year 2011-2012, the Metropolitan Achievement Test result sheets, and the grade sheets in English 2 and in English 4 courses.

The Record of Enrollment was made as the basis in identifying the subjects' sex and course/curricular program.

The Metropolitan Achievement Test is a standardized achievement test that provides reliable and comparable information concerning levels of achievement in three areas of the school curriculum: Reading, Mathematics, and Language.

The result of the said test was used as the basis in identifying the students who attended English Plus and those who did not. The students who attended English Plus were those who got Below Average (BA) rating in both Reading and Language.

The grade sheets in English 2 and English 4 were utilized to gather the data needed for their performances in writing and in literature courses.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the approval of the Campus Director in order to conduct the study, and at the same time to ask permission to have access to the students' records such as the Record of Enrollment and their grades in English 2 and in English 4; and to the guidance counselor, specifically on the result of the Metropolitan Achievement Test.

The data gathered in these documents were computed using the appropriate statistical tools. The results were analyzed and interpreted.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data gathered were subjected to certain statistical tests using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Mean. The mean scores were used to determine the performances of the participants in writing and in literature courses. In this regard, arbitrary distribution and corresponding description were employed.

<u>Rating</u>	<u>Description</u>
1.59 – 1.00	Excellent
2.19 – 1.60	Very Satisfactory
2.79 – 2.20	Satisfactory
3.39 – 2.80	Poor
4.00 – 3.40	Very Poor

Standard Deviation. Standard Deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the samples in terms of their performance.

t-test for Independent Sample. The t-test for independent sample was utilized to find out if there were significant differences in the performance of students in writing and in literature courses when they were categorized as to sex and attendance to remedial course.

One-Way ANOVA. The one-way ANOVA was employed to test the significance of the difference in the performance of students in writing and literature courses when they were categorized as to course/curricular program.

Alpha level was set at .05 for the two-tailed test.

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Data Analysis

The descriptive findings of the study showed the college students' performance in writing and in literature courses. The obtained mean scores were used to determine the performance of college students in the said courses.

Performance of College Students in Writing Course

The data revealed that, generally, the college students' performance in writing course was "very satisfactory".

This does not support the result of the study of Liza (2008) that the proficiency of college students in English was "average."

Further scrutiny of the means revealed that when grouped according to sex, the males ($M = 2.30$, $SD = 0.42512$) had "satisfactory" performance while the females ($M = 2.02$, $SD = 0.37640$) had a "very satisfactory" performance.

This confirmed the study of Kleinfield (2011) that female advantage on standardized tests of reading and writing achievement substantially outstrips the male advantage on standardized tests of science and mathematics.

Also, the result of the present investigation supports the findings in the study of De Silva (2002) that gender has a relative contribution to the language behavior of the students.

Moreover, the findings that females do better than males in supports the study of Plata (2009), Gemora (2006), and Westby (2006).

However, this contradicts the findings of Nullada (2006) stating that no significant difference in English proficiency of the respondents when classified according to sex.

When classified according to course/curriculum program, Teacher Education students ($M = 1.91$, $SD = 0.35237$), and those of Computer and Information Technology ($M = 2.10$, $SD = 0.40593$) had a "very satisfactory" performance; while students of Business and Management ($M = 2.20$, $SD = 0.40572$) had "satisfactory" performance.

This confirmed the studies of Pulmones (2009) and Nulada (2006) that there is a significant difference in the level of English grammar competence of the students when they are classified by college.

However, this contradicts Hsiu & Warden (2009) study that management majors have better English ability also just like with English majors.

Also, Jaschick (2011) study showed that liberal students had significantly higher gains in critical thinking, complex reasoning, and writing skills over time than students majoring in business, education, social work, and communication which showed the smallest gains.

Likewise, the findings revealed that college students who attended the remedial course ($M = 2.10$, $SD = 0.39559$) and those who did not attend ($M = 1.92$, $SD = 0.36367$) had “very satisfactory” performance.

The findings of the study that attendance to remedial course might be in congruence with that of Poral (2004) because it noted gains in the mean score in English grammar after taking English Plus. Although there was a significant difference in the two, the fact that they got “very satisfactory” performance explains they have gained from their attendance in English Plus.

The computed SDs for the performances in writing ranged from 0.35237 to 0.40673 revealed the narrow dispersion of the means indicating the students’ homogeneity in terms of their performance in writing course.

This means that, generally college students at University of Antique Tario-Lim Memorial Campus, except the males and those who are taking Business and Management courses, are highly competent in writing.

Table 2 reflects the data.

Table 2
College Students Performance in Writing Course: Means and Standard Deviations

Category	<u>M</u>	Description	<u>SD</u>
A. Entire Group	2.10	Very Satisfactory	0.40673
B. Sex			
Male	2.30	Satisfactory	0.42512
Female	2.02	Very Satisfactory	0.37640
C. Course/Curricular Program			
Teacher Education	1.91	Very Satisfactory	0.35237
Computer & Information Technology	2.10	Very Satisfactory	0.40593
Business and Management	2.20	Satisfactory	0.40572
D. Attendance to Remedial Course			
Students who attended English Plus	2.10	Very Satisfactory	0.39559
Students who did not attend English Plus	1.92	Very Satisfactory	0.36367

<u>Rating</u>	<u>Description</u>
1.59 – 1.00	Excellent
2.19 – 1.60	Very Satisfactory
2.79 – 2.20	Satisfactory
3.39 – 2.80	Poor
4.00 – 3.40	Very Poor

Performance of College Students in Literature Course

The data in Table 3 revealed that, generally, the college students’ performance in literature course was “very satisfactory”.

Further scrutiny of the means revealed that when grouped according to sex, the males ($M = 2.22$, $SD = 0.42107$) had “satisfactory” performance while the females ($M = 2.01$, $SD = 0.39361$) had “very satisfactory” performance.

This finding is not in congruence with that of Villa (2004) and Cornel (2001) because their studies showed that the level of literary skills college freshmen were only “satisfactory” or “average.”

This means that sex is a factor that affects the college students’ performance in Literature course. This too, confirms the findings of the research made by Hansen (2000) and Kleinfield (2011).

However, Bosede (2010) contradicts on this since his study showed that there is a significant negative relationship among male and female performances in Literature.

When classified according to course/curricular program, Teacher Education ($M = 2.11$, $SD = 0.41924$), Computer and Information Technology ($M = 2.05$, $SD = 0.37338$), and Business and Management students ($M = 2.08$, $SD = 0.45299$) had “very satisfactory” performance in literature course.

This means that the course/curricular program is not a determining factor on the performance of college students in literature course. Whatever is the students’ course/curricular program, they can excel in that area.

Likewise, the findings revealed that both the groups of college students who attended English Plus as a remedial course ($M = 2.18$, $SD = 0.39400$) and those who did not attend the said course ($M = 1.90$, $SD = 0.38699$) had “very satisfactory” performance.

Furthermore, attendance in remedial course does not affect the performance of college students when it comes to literature course since there is no significant difference as revealed in the findings of this study.

The computed SD’s that ranged from 0.37338 to 0.45299 revealed narrow dispersion of the means indicating the students’ homogeneity in terms of their performance in literature course.

This means that, generally college students at University of Antique Tario-Lim Memorial Campus, except the males are highly competent in literature regardless of the course/curricular program taken and attendance in remedial course.

Table 3

College Students Performance in Literature Course: Means and Standard Deviations

Category	<u>M</u>	Description	<u>SD</u>
A. Entire Group	2.07	Very Satisfactory	0.41336
B. Sex			
Male	2.22	Satisfactory	0.42107
Female	2.01	Very Satisfactory	0.39361
C. Course/Curricular Program			
Teacher Education	2.11	Very Satisfactory	0.41924
Computer & Information Technology	2.05	Very Satisfactory	0.37338
Business and Management	2.08	Very Satisfactory	0.45299
D. Attendance to Remedial Course			
Students who attended English Plus	2.18	Very Satisfactory	0.39400
Students who did not attend English Plus	1.90	Very satisfactory	0.38699

Rating

1.59 – 1.00

2.19 – 1.60

Description

Excellent

Very Satisfactory

2.79 – 2.20	Satisfactory
3.39 – 2.80	Poor
4.00 – 3.40	Very Poor

Inferential Data Analysis

The significance of the differences in terms of the students' performances in writing and literature courses were ascertained by the present study.

The computer-processed t-test was utilized to determine the significance of the differences in two-level categories; and the One-Way Analysis of Variance (One-Way ANOVA) for three-level categories. The alpha level was set at .05 alpha.

Differences in the College Students' Writing Performance

The t-test results in Table 4 revealed that a significant difference existed in the writing performance among the students grouped according to sex, $t(221) = 4.301$, $p < .05$, in favor of the females.

Thus, the null hypothesis is not accepted. This means that females are better in writing than the males; and sex is a factor that affects students' performance in the learning area.

There was also a significant difference noted in the college students' writing performance when they were grouped according to attendance to remedial course, $t(221) = 5.359$, $p < .05$, in favor of those who did not attend English Plus.

Thus, the null hypothesis is not accepted. This means that attendance to remedial course is a guarantee that students' performance in writing would be better than those who are already competent in English.

Table 4

t-test Results of the Differences in Performance in Writing

Category	Mean	t-value	df	2-tail probability
A. Sex				
Male	2.30	4.301	221	.000 ^s
Female	2.02			
B. Attendance to English Plus				
Students who attended English Plus	2.21	5.359	221	.000 ^s
Students who did not attend English Plus	1.92			

^s significant ($p > 0.05$)

ANOVA results in Table 5 showed that significant difference existed in the writing performance among the college students grouped according to course/curricular program. Obtained F ratio was 7.817, and probability was less than .05.

Table 5

Analysis of Variance of the Differences in Performance in Writing

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (2-tailed)	F	Sig.
Between Group	2.437	2	1.218		
Within Group	34.288	220	0.156	7.817	0.001 ^s

^s significant ($p > 0.05$)

Employing the Scheffe test for pairwise comparison, it was revealed that Teacher Education students ($M = 1.91$) significantly performed better than Computer and Information Technology ($M = 2.10$), and Business and Management ($M = 2.10$) students. However, no significant difference existed in the performance of students of Computer and Information Technology ($M = 2.10$), and of Business and Management ($M = 2.10$).

This explains that course may affect students' performance in writing.

Differences in College Students' Performance in Literature

The t-test results in Table 6 revealed that a significant difference existed in the literature performance among the students grouped according to sex, $t(221) = 3.704$, $p < .05$, in favor of the females.

Thus, the null hypothesis is not accepted. This explains that sex is a factor that affects students' performance in literature.

There was also a significant difference noted in the college students' literature performance when they were grouped according to attendance to remedial course, $t(221) = 5.172$, $p < .05$, in favor of those who did not attend English Plus.

Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that attendance to remedial course is a guarantee that students' performance in literature would be better than those who are already competent in English.

Table 6

t-test Results of the Differences in Performance in Literature

Category	Mean	t-value	df	2-tail probability
A. Sex				
Male	2.22			
Female	2.01	3.704	221	.000
B. Attendance to English Plus				
Students who attended English Plus	2.18			
Students who did not attend English Plus	1.90	5.172	221	.000

ANOVA results in Table 7 showed that no significant difference existed in the literature performance among the college students grouped according to course/curricular program. Obtained F ratio was 0.355, probability is greater than .05.

This explains that course/curricular program does not affect students' performance in literature.

Table 7
Analysis of Variance of the Differences in Performance in Literature

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (2-tailed)	F	Sig.
Between Group	.122	2	0.061		.355
Within Group	37.810	220	0.172		0.702 ^{ns}

ns.

not significant ($p < 0.05$)

Conclusions

In view of the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Generally, college students at University of Antique, Tario-Lim Memorial Campus, except the males and those who are taking Business and Management courses, are highly competent in writing.
2. The college students, except the males, generally perform very well in literature.
3. The females are better in writing than the males; thus, sex is a factor that affects students' performance in this learning area.

When course is considered, the Teacher Education students perform better compared to those in Computer and Information Technology, and in Business and Management courses. However, those in Computer and Information Technology, and in Business and Management courses have comparable performances in writing. Thus, course may affect students' performance in writing.

Since students who attended English Plus also perform very well in writing, their engagement to a remedial course may have helped them attain the competencies in writing. However, it is noted that they do not perform significantly better than those who did not attend English Plus; thus, attendance to a remedial course is not a guarantee that students' performance in writing would be better than those who are already competent in English.

4. In literature, females perform better than males; thus, sex is a factor that affects students' performance in the said learning area.

Since students who attended English Plus perform well in literature, the preparation they have obtained in this remedial course may have helped them deal with their lessons in literature. However, it is also noted they do not perform significantly better than those who did not attend English Plus; thus, attendance to a remedial course is not a guarantee that students' performance in literature would be better than those who are already competent in English.

However, course does not affect the performance in literature of the college students.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Since the result of the study indicated that males were not competent in their performance in the writing course, it is recommended that instructors should extend more help to them in order to obtain

the necessary competencies in writing. Moreover, male students are advised to study hard and master those basic skills in writing so that they will be confident in their performing the tasks in their chosen field.

Moreover, Business and Management students should also focus on improving their skills in writing since part of their job in the future would be about writing, especially those assigned in the offices. Teachers, too, should pay attention on the needs of their students for the latter's success in writing lies on their hands.

2. Males' performance in literature needs to be improved. Teachers handling the class should present the lessons interestingly for the male students to relate and see the value of literature as a course, and in their lives. Male students should also intrinsically motivate themselves to love and study literature with passion for their performance in the course could greatly help them to be better persons in the society.

3. It is recommended that English Plus should still be offered to students who have deficiencies in English because even when these students have undergone remediation their performance is still inadequate compared to those who were already competent. Thus, the curriculum of English Plus as a remedial course must be well-developed, and its existence must be promoted to other colleges and universities.

Administrators and curriculum planners should give more attention on the implementation of remedial classes. It should be strengthened to fully develop the skills of college students for them to hurdle college life, and therefore improve their skills in both writing and literature courses. The school administration should check how teachers who handle the remediation class do well in the teaching and learning process. Also, the syllabus being used in English Plus should be given attention by having some revisions for them to fit to the needs of the college students who are taking the subject.

4. It is also recommended that the result of this study be shared to the teachers, specifically the English teachers in high school and the writing and literature instructors and professors in college, so that they will know the status of their students' performance in English and in those specific areas. In this case, they can check whether the instruction in the said learning area is effective or not. Thus, they can make some innovations in their classrooms to further improve the students' knowledge and skills in writing and in literature in English, and eventually master these competencies for future use.

Areas for Further Research

In order to validate the results of the present inquiry, parallel studies on college students' performances in writing and literature be conducted in a wider range. Based on the result of the present investigation, the following areas for further research are recommended:

1. Remedial teaching,
2. Use of standardized test such as Metropolitan Achievement Test as requirement for admission to college, and
3. The teaching of writing and literature in the tertiary education.

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